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Reassessing Decarbonization Pathways: the Role of micro-SMRs in an Electrification-constrained EU Energy Framework

Summary

The increasingly prominent role of renewable energy sources in the decarbonization of the power sector, district heating, and other branches of the economy is beginning to give rise to a range of challenges. Proposed decarbonization pathways for transport, industry, and buildings—particularly through the development of hydrogen and e-fuels markets—face significant difficulties due to the substantial additional demand they place on electricity generated from renewable energy sources. This may result in competition for the same limited resources, thereby contributing to increased costs. The remedies proposed in current EU regulations raise critical questions about the availability of viable alternative approaches. Issues such as grid stability, the social acceptability of rising costs, and the actual carbon footprint across entire supply chains are intensifying the search for alternatives. Among the emerging options, the deployment of micro-SMRs—modular nuclear reactors with a capacity of up to 50 MW—in hybrid systems is increasingly recognized as an economically and socially viable alternative. However, the success of such a transition requires more decisive political and regulatory support at the EU level. EU energy transition policies must provide a clearer impetus for the national adoption and integration of these technologies. This article identifies specific regulatory changes needed to ensure that EU law and policy formally acknowledge and support small modular reactors as a permanent component of the energy transition framework.

Key words: EU Energy Policy, micro-SMR, EU regulation, RFNBO, e-fuels, decarbonisation, SMR

1. Introduction

1.1. EU Decarbonization Policy: Structural Barriers and Emerging Regulatory Challenges

The European Union (EU) has committed to reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, and to achieving full climate neutrality by 2050. To date, decarbonization efforts have delivered measurable progress in the energy and industrial sectors.

However, the transport sector remains off-track in its decarbonization trajectory, while the building sector has achieved only limited success.¹

Deep decarbonization in sectors such as industry and construction is increasingly challenged by significant technological barriers and high associated costs, which impact both the pace and scale of implementation.² Despite the growing share of renewables in electricity generation, fossil fuels remain the primary energy source, and the contribution of nuclear power has remained relatively stable.

Historically, the temporary increase in the use of natural gas was considered a transitional solution due to its lower emission intensity compared to coal. However, this approach has proven vulnerable to substantial political risks (e.g., the war in Ukraine) and economic uncertainties (e.g., unpredictable price volatility). An alternative decarbonization path—based on the gradual replacement of natural gas with biomethane—has emerged to enhance the role of gas as a transitional fuel. Nevertheless, biomethane production in the EU currently remains insufficient, and the technical and economic barriers to large-scale deployment are significant, rendering it an unfeasible option at scale in the short term.

The EU has placed significant emphasis on the expansion of renewable energy sources (RES). However, the continued development of distributed generation based on renewables is constrained by real and persistent infrastructural limitations. The transmission and distribution networks are often incapable of accommodating new connections, resulting in delays and refusals by operators, while regulatory authorities remain cautious regarding deeper integration of decentralized RES due to concerns over supply security and grid stability. Increasing political and regulatory pressure on network operators to accelerate grid modernization raises a fundamental question: to what extent are end-users willing to bear the additional costs? Hybrid models—particularly those based on off-grid operation—introduce questions about scalability, especially in the context of rising electricity consumption and the imperative to ensure reliability and supply continuity.

The growth of distributed generation, energy communities, and other local energy initiatives—intended to relieve pressure on central networks while enhancing the share of RES—faces regulatory complexity and diminishing market profitability in the absence of further public financial support (e.g., incentives for heat pump adoption). Even where renewable technologies (such as wind or solar) are currently cost-effective, the uncertainties associated with balancing their intermittent output—via energy storage, balancing services, or the production of hydrogen and synthetic fuels—cast doubt on their long-term profitability. An increasingly pressing issue in RES deployment is the environmental footprint of rare earth metal extraction, which is vital for scaling up these technologies. Although these environmental impacts are primarily associated with countries outside the EU, their global relevance is growing and cannot be ignored. Incorporating such factors into carbon governance models and supply

¹ Bogenstätter, U., Chalkidis, S., & Slim, R. (2025). *How climate targets in the building sector can be achieved after all*. <https://digitalcollection.zhaw.ch/server/api/core/bitstreams/d5d26a8f-601c-4faf-9e90-bbfc00c7ac6/content#page=122>; Mayeres, I. (2025), 'European Union Transition to Green Energy in the Transport Sector', in Zen, F., F. Kimura, and A.J. Purwanto (eds.), *Fiscal Policy to Support the Green and Just Energy Transition*. ERIA Research Project Report FY2024 No. 28, Jakarta: ERIA, pp.188-229; Cartalis, C., Dessai, S., Diaz Anadon, L., & Edenhofer, O. (2024). *Towards EU climate neutrality: Progress, policy gaps and opportunities*, <https://ntnuopen.ntnu.no/ntnu-xmlui/handle/11250/3125599>.

² Brown, C., Hampton, S., & Fawcett, T. (2024). Accelerating renewable heat: Overcoming barriers to shared-loop ground source heat pump systems in the United Kingdom, *Energy Research & Social Science* 115 (2024) 103644.

chain assessments could significantly alter the perceived sustainability of certain technologies.³ Whether this situation is merely transitional remains to be seen. It is conceivable that further technological innovation may restore the economic viability of current models. The key question, however, is *when*. With 2030 just around the corner and the 2050 climate neutrality goal rapidly approaching, time is becoming a critical constraint. If time alone proves insufficient, the question becomes whether adequate public funding will be available to sufficiently stimulate private sector interest and accelerate innovation in this direction.

1.2. Micro-SMRs as a Supplementary Option in EU Decarbonization Policy: Regulatory Rationale and Systemic Value

A solution that merits serious consideration as a politically viable long-term approach to decarbonization is the development of micro-SMRs (micro small modular reactors), defined as nuclear installations with an electrical capacity below 50 MWe.⁴ To facilitate the market deployment of such technologies, there is a clear need for an enabling regulatory environment and a coherent EU policy that recognizes micro-SMRs as a legitimate long-term option in the energy transition.

This approach is justified by the inherent characteristics of micro-SMR technology, which align not only with the technical requirements of power and heat systems, but also with broader political goals for decarbonization. Based on analysis of source data provided by technology developers, several features are of particular importance. Key attributes include standardization of design, modularity, the potential for mass production, and serial factory-based construction. Similar to standard SMRs (up to 300 MWe), micro-SMRs offer a simplified investment process since construction occurs largely in manufacturer facilities, with modular units delivered to the deployment site and assembled akin to “building LEGO blocks.”

The reduced size of these reactors translates into lower safety and environmental risks, which allows for simplified designs and operational procedures. The use of specially designed, smaller quantities of nuclear fuel further enhances safety. In emergency or abnormal scenarios, these reactors can shut down autonomously without external power, thereby mitigating the risk of radioactive release. Importantly, micro-SMRs can operate independently of the transmission and distribution grid, offering increased deployment flexibility. Compared to traditional large nuclear reactors, they also provide superior production flexibility—capable of adjusting power output dynamically in response to fluctuations in electricity demand or variable renewable energy generation. This enables micro-SMRs to contribute to real-time grid balancing, enhance system flexibility, and optimize production profiles.

When electricity demand is high, micro-SMRs can prioritize power output. In scenarios where heat demand is present, energy can be redirected to serve district heating or industrial processes. When electricity from renewables is abundant and heat is unnecessary, these reactors can shift to producing hydrogen or synthetic fuels for transport or industrial use. Their modular architecture also enables

³ E. M. Carlini *et al.*, “Combined Network and Storage Development: Renewable Integration Efficiency Assessment,” *2024 IEEE International Humanitarian Technologies Conference (IHTC)*, Bari, Italy, 2024, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/IHTC61819.2024.10855092; Vaya Soler, A., Berthelemy, M., Verma, A., Bilbao y Leon, S., Kwong, G., Sozoniuk, V., White, A., Rouyer, V., Sexton Nick, K., Vasquez-Maignan, X., & Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development, Nuclear Energy Agency - OECD/NEA, 46, quai Alphonse Le Gallo, 92100 Boulogne Billancourt (France). (2021). *Small Modular Reactors: Challenges and Opportunities*.

⁴ Some of the installations may have capacities as low as below 1 MWe. The most commonly used technologies range from 1 to 20 MWe. For example: Ultra Safe Micro Modular Reactor (Ultra Safe Nuclear Corp.) - 5 MWe, eVinci Microreactor (Westinghouse) - 1-5 MWe, Oklo Aurora (Oklo Inc.) - 1,5 MWe, NuScale Micro SMR (NuScale Power) - 10-20 MWe, U-Battery (Urenco) - 4 MWe.

scalability: modules can be added, idled, or downsized depending on real-time system needs. Micro-SMRs are particularly well-suited to remote or industrial locations, with the capacity to operate both autonomously and in grid-connected modes. Furthermore, micro-SMRs utilize long-life nuclear fuel, minimizing operational disruptions and refueling needs. Certain designs can function for 10 to 20 years without refueling. Advanced versions may utilize high-assay low-enriched uranium (HALEU), thorium, or even recycled spent nuclear fuel, enhancing resource efficiency.⁵

Given these features, it is inappropriate to regulate micro-SMRs using the same framework as large-scale nuclear reactors, especially concerning safety assessments and their ability to integrate with RES. Nevertheless, current EU regulatory and policy frameworks often fail to distinguish between the two. Encouragingly, early signs of political will for regulatory reform have emerged in some Member States, with new legislation tailored specifically to SMRs—though this remains at an early stage. There is a strong case for separate regulatory recognition of micro-SMRs, particularly in light of their high adaptability to hybrid energy systems that combine power, heat, and fuel production. As such, micro-SMRs are becoming a natural component of decentralized, hybrid energy infrastructures. These hybrid systems aim to integrate zero- and low-emission energy technologies and align decentralized production with localized energy consumption patterns to minimize adverse grid impacts. Legislative instruments such as those on energy communities, self-consumption, aggregation, and prosumers are designed to facilitate the growth of these local energy ecosystems. Ultimately, these systems could combine electricity, heat, cooling, hydrogen, and synthetic fuel production within closed-loop, off-grid frameworks. As a stable and flexible baseload energy source, micro-SMRs are uniquely positioned to serve as the technological backbone of such integrated models. Their deployment also holds significant potential in hydrogen production as part of hybrid configurations.⁶

1.3. Regulatory Barriers to the Development of Micro-SMRs in the EU: Key Challenges and Policy Gaps

An in-depth review of numerous scientific publications allows the identification of three core categories of regulatory challenges that constrain the wider deployment of micro-SMRs (micro small modular reactors) within the European economy.

First, as highlighted across a range of studies⁷, micro-SMR technologies have not yet been commercialized within the EU. Their current technological maturity lies within Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 6–9, indicating that full technological readiness, validated by regulatory approval for commercial deployment, is unlikely to be achieved before 2028–2030. Market entry is therefore expected no earlier than 2028–2035. This timeline creates regulatory uncertainty due to the absence of precedents, which in turn prompts a particularly cautious approach by national and EU regulatory bodies.

⁵ Vaya Soler, A., Berthelemy, M., Verma, A., Bilbao y Leon, S., Kwong, G., Sozoniuk, V., White, A., Rouyer, V., Sexton Nick, K., Vasquez-Maignan, X., & Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development, Nuclear Energy Agency - OECD/NEA, 46, quai Alphonse Le Gallo, 92100 Boulogne Billancourt (France). (2021). *Small Modular Reactors: Challenges and Opportunities*;

⁶ Ishaq M., Dincer I., A clean hydrogen and electricity co-production system based on an integrated plant with small modular nuclear reactor, *Energy* 308 (2024) 132834; Michaelson D., Jiang J., Review of integration of small modular reactors in renewable energy microgrids, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 152 (2021) 111638.

⁷ For example: Testoni R., Bersano A., Segantin S. Review of nuclear microreactors: Status, potentialities and challenges, *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, 138 (2021) 103822;

Second, the existing national licensing and regulatory frameworks remain misaligned with the scale and specific risk profile of micro-SMR technology.⁸ These frameworks are primarily designed for large-scale nuclear installations, resulting in disproportionate regulatory requirements and associated costs when applied to micro-reactors.⁹ This mismatch creates unfavorable market conditions for micro-SMR development. In addition, the prevailing prescriptive regulatory model—although crucial for safety—requires greater flexibility within a more polycentric decision-making framework. A further complicating factor is the presence of regulatory capability gaps, stemming from a lack of prior experience with micro-nuclear technologies. This lack of familiarity often results in overly cautious or restrictive regulatory interpretations.¹⁰ A particularly salient issue is the absence of in-factory certification processes, which is critical for technologies that rely on modular, factory-based construction. The lack of such procedures negatively impacts deployment timelines, project costs, and ultimately the economic feasibility of micro-SMRs. In this context, the adoption of international standards and the facilitation of ongoing knowledge exchange between regulatory authorities are essential. Encouragingly, initial steps in this direction are already underway.

Third, the absence of a clear and supportive EU-level policy framework for micro-SMRs represents a major strategic gap. Without coherent guidance at the European level, the development of micro-SMRs is hindered by regulatory fragmentation, limited access to funding, and sluggish market uptake. This could significantly delay their contribution to decarbonization, grid flexibility, and industrial energy needs. More critically, the lack of EU policy coordination increases the risk of regulatory delays, investment uncertainty, and prolonged dependence on fossil fuels. To date, there are relatively few academic studies explicitly focused on micro-SMR policy within the EU. Related issues are often explored indirectly in the context of hydrogen development¹¹, or the rising electricity demand driven by the expansion of ICT and artificial intelligence infrastructure¹². However, the decarbonization and modernization of district heating systems, as well as the integration of micro-SMRs with renewables,

⁸ Mignacca, B., Locatelli, G., & Sainati, T. (2020). Deeds not words: Barriers and remedies for Small Modular Nuclear Reactors. *Energy*, 206, 118137.

⁹ In-depth analysis on regulatory approach models, see: Yeung K., Ranchordas S., *An Introduction to Law and Regulation*. Text and Materials. 2024 Cambridge University Press.

¹⁰ For example: Earlier publication: Ramana M.V., Berzak Hopkins L., Glaser A. Licensing small modular reactors, *Energy* 61 (2013) 555-564; Söderholm K., Tuunanen J., Amabab B., Bergqvist S., Lusardi P. Licensing process characteristics of Small Modular Reactors and spent nuclear fuel repository. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 276 (2014) 1–8. Sainati, T., Locatelli, G., Brookes, N., Small modular reactors: licensing constraints and the way forward. *Energy* 2015 82, 1092–1095. Mignacca B., Locatelli G., Sainati T., Deeds not words: Barriers and remedies for Small Modular nuclear Reactors, *Energy* 206 (2020) 118137. Complex analysis of state of art: Rohunsingh S., Sainati T., Hanson B., Kay R. , Licensing small modular reactors: A state-of-the-art review of the challenges and barriers . *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 164 (2023) 104859.

¹¹ Ajanovic A., Sayer M., Haas R., The economics and the environmental benignity of different colors of hydrogen, *International journal of hydrogen energy* 47(2022) 2 4136-24154; Dawood F, Anda M., Shafiullah G.M. Hydrogen production for energy: an overview. *Int J Hydrogen Energy* 2020;45(7):3847e69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.12.059>; Singh P., Agarwal A.K., Thakur A., & Sinha R.K. Challenges and Opportunities in Green Hydrogen Production. Springer 2024; El-Emam R.S., Ozcan H., Zamfirescu C. Updates on promising thermochemical cycles for clean hydrogen production using nuclear energy. *J Clean Prod* 2020 262 121424;

¹² Cha S., The potential role of small modular reactors (SMRs) in addressing the increasing power demand of the artificial intelligence industry: A scenario-based analysis, *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*. Available online 12 November 2024, 103314; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.net.2024.11.016>.

energy storage, and synthetic fuel production, are now emerging as key components of hybrid energy system designs. These models are gradually attracting more academic and policy interest.¹³

This article summarizes the most relevant EU-level policies impacting the future of micro-SMRs and aims to expand awareness of specific policy aspects within the EU regulatory framework that, if revised or clarified, could significantly increase stakeholder interest and accelerate the deployment of micro-SMR technologies across the Union.

2. Research Approach

This paper employs a systematic literature review methodology to identify and analyze relevant academic publications and institutional reports concerning the regulatory dimensions of micro-SMR deployment within the European Union. The review was conducted between January and March 2025, primarily using the Scopus database, supplemented by reports from authoritative institutions and policy bodies.

The academic literature surveyed tends to offer broad and conceptual overviews of regulatory issues, with only limited engagement in the specificities of EU-level legal and policy frameworks. Nevertheless, by systematically synthesizing these sources, this article contributes a focused analytical perspective on the evolving European political and regulatory context for advanced nuclear technologies—particularly micro-SMRs.

The core scientific contribution of this work lies in its ability to highlight key policy gaps, regulatory barriers, and potential reform pathways, thereby situating micro-SMRs more firmly within the broader discourse on EU energy law and decarbonization strategies. This perspective is intended to support both academic inquiry and policymaking by clarifying how legal frameworks may evolve to accommodate emerging low-carbon technologies within hybrid and decentralized energy systems.

3. The Need for a Clear EU Policy Framework for SMRs and Micro-SMRs

The necessity of a broader regulatory perspective on Small Modular Reactors (SMRs)—including micro-SMRs—is no longer solely advocated by stakeholders or academic communities. It has been explicitly recognized in a 2023 Resolution of the European Parliament¹⁴, which addresses both micro-SMRs and standard SMRs (ranging from 10 to 300 MW).

The resolution acknowledges that, in light of the expected doubling of the EU's electricity demand—driven by rising consumption and the electrification of heating, cooling, and transport—SMRs represent a key technological solution across multiple sectors. These include not only electricity generation and district heating, but also hydrogen production, clean transport, and water desalination.

¹³ Vaglio-Gaudard C., Dominguez Bautista M.T., Frignani M., Fütterer M., Goicea A., Hanus E., Hollands T., Lombardo C., Lorenzi S., Miss J., Pavel G., Pucciarelli A., Ricotti M., Ruby A., Schneidesch C., Sholomitsky S., Simonini G., Tulkki V., Varri K., Zezula L., Wessberg N. The TANDEM Euratom project: Context, objectives and workplan. *Nuclear Engineering and Technology* 56 (2024) 993–1001; Ho A., Hill D., Hedengren J., Powell K.M., A nuclear-hydrogen hybrid energy system with large-scale storage: A study in optimal dispatch and economic performance in a real-world market, *Journal of Energy Storage* 51 (2022) 104510; Pinsky R., Sabharwall P., Hartvigsen J., O'Brien J. Comparative review of hydrogen production technologies for nuclear hybrid energy systems. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 2020;123:103317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2020.103317>; Masotti G., Cammi A., Lorenzi S., Ricotti E., Modeling and simulation of nuclear hybrid energy systems architectures, *Energy Conversion and Management* Volume 298, 15 December 2023, 117684.

¹⁴ European Parliament, P9_TA(2023)0456 – Small modular reactors – European Parliament resolution of 12 December 2023 on small modular reactors (2023/2109(INI)), OJ C/2024/4161, 2.8.2024.

Crucially, the European Parliament clearly affirms that nuclear energy constitutes a zero-emissions technology that does not contribute to air pollution, and therefore, SMRs hold significant potential for supporting the EU's climate and environmental objectives. The resolution calls for the development of a comprehensive deployment strategy for SMRs within the EU, emphasizing the need to tailor this strategy to the specific regional characteristics, including remote and sparsely populated areas, as well as the unique needs of various industrial sectors.

From the perspective of EU energy and climate governance, the resolution underscores that a prerequisite for the successful development of SMRs is the establishment of a technology-neutral, stable, and long-term regulatory framework. This implies that EU policy should not discriminate between technologies that contribute equally toward common decarbonization objectives. As this article will demonstrate, several specific EU regulatory measures currently place SMRs—and especially micro-SMRs—at a disadvantage relative to other technologies, such as renewable energy systems and hydrogen.

In addition, the European Parliament advocates for the creation of a standardized licensing framework for SMRs, to address the growing problem of regulatory divergence across Member States. Such fragmentation, if left unaddressed, could severely hinder the scalability and market integration of micro-SMR technologies, despite their modular design and high potential for replication. Regulatory harmonization, by contrast, could facilitate more widespread deployment and allow SMRs to contribute effectively to the EU's climate targets and energy security agenda.

The resolution further stresses the need for concrete action by the European Commission to formulate a dedicated industrial strategy for SMRs, including: streamlined and efficient permitting procedures, guaranteed access to financing instruments and the establishment of resilient supply chains to support domestic deployment of SMR technologies. Moreover, it calls for increased public awareness and institutional support for SMRs within the EU's industrial and energy policy agenda.

Given the legal and institutional role of the European Parliament in shaping EU legislation, the resolution should not be dismissed as a mere political declaration. Instead, it must be viewed as a strategic directive that identifies specific areas within the current EU legal framework that require adaptation or reform in order to ensure a coherent, enabling policy environment for the advancement of SMRs—including micro-SMRs.

The subsequent sections of this paper will critically evaluate the existing EU regulatory instruments in light of the objectives and principles articulated in the 2023 resolution, and demonstrate the extent to which the current framework falls short of enabling SMRs to play a full role in the European energy transition.

4. The EU Taxonomy and the Regulatory Ambiguity Surrounding Micro-SMRs

A foundational regulation with significant implications for the financing of micro-SMRs (micro small modular reactors) is the EU Taxonomy Regulation¹⁵, which aims to guide capital flows toward environmentally sustainable investments that support the EU's decarbonization objectives. By establishing uniform criteria for classifying economic activities as "green" or "sustainable," the Taxonomy plays a critical role in enhancing regulatory certainty, thereby influencing investor behavior and the bankability of new technologies.

¹⁵ Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 *on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088*.

While the regulation is intended to support investment in low-carbon technologies, it makes no explicit reference to nuclear power, including micro-SMRs.¹⁶ Article 10 of the Regulation refers broadly to the promotion of technologies that ensure the development of “fuels from carbon-neutral sources” while avoiding carbon-intensive lock-in effects during the energy transition. This provision could, in principle, encompass micro-SMRs, given that they qualify as low-carbon or even transitional technologies within the meaning of the Regulation.

Further interpretative support stems from Article 19, which mandates technological neutrality. Under this clause, nuclear technologies—provided they meet rigorous scientific, environmental, and lifecycle assessment criteria—may be deemed sustainable. These include, *inter alia*, a comprehensive life cycle analysis of greenhouse gas emissions and a demonstration of “no significant harm” to the Regulation’s six environmental objectives. Article 17 reiterates this, stipulating that activities must avoid significant adverse effects on objectives such as pollution prevention, biodiversity protection, and hazardous waste minimization.

Despite this potentially inclusive legal architecture, nuclear energy was originally excluded from the EU Taxonomy framework due to longstanding concerns over waste management, safety, and environmental risks. If this exclusionary stance persists, micro-SMRs may suffer from reduced investment attractiveness and elevated financing costs. These consequences are particularly consequential for micro-SMRs given their intended role in hybrid energy systems, where cost-effective integration with renewables, storage, and hydrogen production is crucial.

Nonetheless, a more positive trajectory has recently emerged. The Delegated Act on Nuclear Energy under the Taxonomy acknowledges nuclear energy as a transitional low-carbon technology. It recognizes the role of nuclear power in climate change mitigation, albeit under a provisional classification—that is, as a stopgap measure until fully renewable alternatives become commercially viable. Nuclear activities, including those involving SMRs and micro-SMRs, must still meet stringent criteria related to waste disposal, safety systems, and long-term environmental safeguards.

Importantly, the current regulatory framework continues to treat micro-SMRs identically to large-scale nuclear installations, despite their markedly different scale, risk profile, and operational characteristics. Although temporary inclusion within the taxonomy provides limited recognition of their environmental compatibility, this status is conditional and non-permanent. The predominant regulatory concern remains spent fuel management, although ongoing technological innovations—such as the use of low-assay or depleted nuclear fuels and enhanced safety mechanisms—are actively addressing these risks.

Given these developments, there is a compelling argument for reclassifying micro-SMRs as long-term sustainable solutions rather than merely transitional technologies. Failure to do so risks perpetuating regulatory ambiguity, discouraging investment, and hindering integration into evolving hybrid and decentralized energy systems. Grouping micro-SMRs with large-scale nuclear power under a common regulatory regime increasingly appears technically unjustified and economically counterproductive.

To ensure a more coherent regulatory approach, it is necessary to differentiate micro-SMRs from conventional nuclear reactors within the EU Taxonomy. This distinction would send a strong market signal supporting investment in smaller, flexible, and modular nuclear systems. The timing is appropriate: technological readiness is advancing, and differentiation based on operational scale and environmental impact is both feasible and necessary.

A nuanced regulatory framework should also recognize the scalability of SMR technologies. A location hosting a single micro-SMR unit (e.g., 40 MW) should not be subject to the same regulatory treatment as a site that has expanded to multiple modules with a combined capacity approaching or exceeding

¹⁶ Stevanka K., Chvala O., Deployment of small modular reactors in the European Union, *Nuclear Science and Technology Open Research* 2024, 2:24, <https://doi.org/10.12688/nuclscitechnopenres.17510.1>.

the 300 MW threshold typically used to define standard SMRs. Regulatory approaches must account for cumulative impacts, while still enabling technology-neutral assessment across nuclear and renewable technologies.

Lastly, the article highlights the importance of robust carbon footprint accounting across all energy technologies. Applying standardized lifecycle assessment tools to evaluate emissions and environmental performance would help ensure that technology neutrality in the EU Taxonomy is not only a legal principle but also a scientifically credible and economically rational policy approach.

5. EU Industrial Policy and Its Emerging Role in Supporting Micro-SMR Development

The European Union's recently updated industrial policy framework underscores the strategic importance of industrial competitiveness and resilience for the Union's long-term economic and social development.¹⁷ Although the policy does not explicitly address nuclear energy, it contains provisions with significant implications for the advancement of micro-Small Modular Reactors (micro-SMRs).

Most notably, the policy (European Commission, 2024, pp. 4–5) reaffirms that, while Member States retain full sovereignty over their national energy mixes, the European Commission will assess State aid for nuclear supply chains and technologies in accordance with the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) and with respect for the principle of technological neutrality. This marks a pivotal shift in the regulatory landscape: micro-SMR projects will now be subject to EU State aid rules under a framework that explicitly embraces technological neutrality.

Such recognition opens the door for several strategic developments:

1. Nationally backed investment schemes supporting micro-SMR research, demonstration, and deployment could receive formal EU-level acceptance.
2. EU funding instruments, such as the *Just Transition Fund* and the *Recovery and Resilience Facility*, could become accessible for micro-SMR projects.
3. The policy may stimulate the growth of EU-based micro-SMR supply chains, reducing dependency on non-European nuclear technologies (e.g., U.S., Canadian, or Russian platforms).

However, the effectiveness of this policy hinges on the granularity of the regulatory framework. The economic risks and cost structures associated with large-scale nuclear power differ significantly from those applicable to micro-SMRs. Therefore, State aid rules should be tailored to reflect the differentiated cost dynamics across the entire supply chain, including the scalability and modular deployment potential of micro-reactors.

A promising approach for balancing investor risk and public policy goals is the use of Contract for Difference (CfD) mechanisms, which offer long-term price stability and enable market-based assessment of economic viability. Another potential solution is the standardization of Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), akin to those commonly used in renewable energy markets. These agreements can guarantee stable offtake and pricing over the lifetime of the installation and serve to reduce investor exposure to regulatory risk, especially in long-term infrastructure contracts.

Given the versatility of micro-SMRs—enabling not only electricity, heating, and cooling production, but also hydrogen generation, synthetic fuels, and grid-balancing services—a comprehensive and harmonized PPA framework that involves national regulatory authorities is essential. Regulatory volatility in one Member State may have spillover effects across others, especially where cross-border energy trade or multi-jurisdictional projects are concerned.

¹⁷ European Commission, The Clean Industrial Deal: A joint roadmap for competitiveness and decarbonisation of 26.2.2025 COM(2025) 85 final.

Beyond the technological costs, the costs of regulatory compliance represent a critical component of total project expenditures. The current lack of differentiation in regulatory treatment based on reactor scale may impose disproportionately high burdens on micro-SMR projects. A targeted public support mechanism, specifically designed to cover the costs of legal and regulatory compliance, could ensure a more equitable and efficient deployment of these technologies.

One potential model is the establishment of a "regulatory agreement"—a legal instrument through which competent authorities would transparently define how future regulatory changes (both at EU and national levels) will affect key contractual components, such as PPAs. This could significantly mitigate regulatory risk and improve the bankability of micro-SMR projects.

In conclusion, the evolution of the EU's industrial policy and State aid framework presents an opportunity to construct a coherent support architecture for micro-SMRs, integrating financial tools, regulatory guidance, and legal certainty. However, to unlock the full potential of this technology within hybrid energy systems, a differentiated, scale-sensitive, and risk-adjusted regulatory model must be urgently developed. A more nuanced approach to technology-specific aid, especially in relation to micro-SMRs, is not only desirable but necessary to ensure their effective integration into the EU's decarbonized energy future.

6. The EU Electricity Market and the Position of Nuclear Technologies, Including Micro-SMRs

The role of nuclear energy within the European Union's overall electricity mix has remained relatively stable over the past decade. Between 2010 and 2017, its contribution fluctuated within a narrow band of 12.9% to 13.8% of total primary energy supply. In terms of electricity actually delivered to the market, nuclear energy's contribution in 2017 amounted to 208.7 Mtoe, which was approximately 10% lower than the volume generated from renewable energy sources (233.9 Mtoe) during the same period.¹⁸

From a long-term strategic perspective, EU energy policy is tasked with balancing three critical objectives: (1) diversifying the energy mix, (2) reducing dependence on external energy imports, and (3) expanding the use of domestic, low-carbon energy sources. While the share of renewables has grown significantly due to strong policy support, the absence of an EU policy framework that explicitly promotes nuclear technologies has not prevented nuclear power from maintaining its market share. On the contrary, interest in advanced nuclear technologies, including Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), is visibly growing within the EU.¹⁹

Despite this trend, EU electricity market regulations do not explicitly reference nuclear energy, and by extension, micro-SMRs are also absent from the current legislative framework. The prevailing regulatory model—most notably defined in Regulation (EU) 2019/943 on the internal market for electricity—emphasizes technological neutrality, facilitating market access, grid integration, and fair competition among electricity producers regardless of generation technology.

Complementary instruments include:

- Directive (EU) 2019/944, which supports decentralized generation, prosumer participation, and smart grid technologies;
- Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (RED II) and its recast RED III, which promote the integration of renewable sources and obligate transmission system operators to ensure grid access;

¹⁸ EU Statistical Office.

¹⁹ Weibezahn, J., Steigerwald, B. (2024). *Fission for funds: The financing of nuclear power plants*. Energy Policy 195 (2024) 114382.

- Regulation (EU) 2022/869 on Trans-European Energy Networks (TEN-E), which supports cross-border hybrid renewable projects and associated infrastructure investments.

In practice, however, while these instruments nominally embrace technological neutrality, they functionally prioritize specific technologies—namely renewables—through tailored regulatory and financial mechanisms. These include bespoke business model designs and incentive structures aimed at improving generation efficiency, system integration, and consumption flexibility. Meanwhile, nuclear energy remains regulated largely under a separate legal framework derived from the Euratom Treaty, focusing predominantly on safety, security, and non-proliferation, rather than market design and system integration.

Nevertheless, hybrid energy systems—though not explicitly defined in EU energy law—are increasingly emerging as functional components of the internal market, especially at the intersection of electricity, gas, and heat markets. These systems integrate various technologies for the co-production of electricity, heat, cooling, hydrogen, and synthetic fuels, while ensuring optimal demand-supply balancing at both the local and national levels. Micro-SMRs are particularly well-suited for such applications due to their modularity, flexible deployment, and capacity for multi-vector energy services.

Against this backdrop, it becomes imperative to identify and eliminate national regulatory practices that could create disproportionate barriers to the deployment of micro-SMRs. A consistent application of technological neutrality—a cornerstone of EU energy market design—should be extended to include micro-nuclear technologies, ensuring regulatory harmonization across Member States. Doing so would enable the scalability and replication of micro-SMR projects across the Union and mitigate the risk of regulatory fragmentation or overregulation arising from diverging national policies.

In conclusion, while the EU's electricity market legislation provides a formal framework for open and competitive energy markets, it currently lacks specific provisions to accommodate emerging nuclear technologies such as micro-SMRs. As hybrid systems and decentralization gain momentum, micro-SMRs should be explicitly considered in future regulatory reforms, especially where they offer solutions to grid balancing, system resilience, and multi-energy integration in line with EU climate and energy goals.

7. The EU Heat Market and the Untapped Potential of Micro-SMRs in Decarbonization Strategies

In 2022, the total heat produced within the European Union amounted to 589 TWh. Of this, approximately 56% originated from fossil fuels, 34% from renewable energy sources, and a mere 0.17% from nuclear energy.²⁰ Despite a downward trend in the use of fossil fuels for heat generation, their share remains dominant. Significantly, over 50% of total final energy consumption in the EU is allocated to heating and cooling, making this sector a cornerstone of the Union's broader decarbonization agenda.²¹

²⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Electricity_and_heat_statistics

²¹ http://tandemproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/D1_1_Analysis_of_the_key_features_of_the_future_EU_energy_market_and_associated_regional_national_landscapes_V1_V1.pdf, page 12.

The EU heat market is fundamentally national and often regional in scope, due to the inherent inefficiencies and economic impracticalities of transporting heat over long distances.²² Even in Member States with well-developed district heating systems, networks are typically confined to urban clusters or densely populated areas. As such, heat regulation is largely decentralized, falling under the jurisdiction of national and subnational authorities. This decentralization presents a particular challenge for the decarbonization of heating, especially in regions where coal-fired generation remains prevalent.²³

While the EU does not directly regulate heat as an energy carrier, it does so indirectly through directives and strategies focused on energy efficiency, building performance, and carbon footprint reduction. This includes legislative efforts aimed at improving the energy performance of buildings, which account for approximately 40% of final energy use and 35% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the EU. Moreover, 75% of the building stock is energy inefficient, and between 85% and 95% of these buildings are expected to still be in use by 2050. The average annual renovation rate is low—around 1%²⁴, while 53% of space heating in buildings continues to rely on fossil fuels, including gas, oil, and coal. Buildings are also a major contributor to fine particulate (PM_{2.5}) emissions, responsible for up to 50% of low-stack emissions, a key public health concern across the EU.

Multiple factors influence the energy efficiency of buildings, including thermal insulation, heating and cooling systems, renewable energy integration, automation, ventilation heat recovery, and passive design features. However, the current range of technologies only partially meets cost-efficiency requirements—particularly when considering full life-cycle assessments. A critical factor often overlooked in decarbonization strategies is the type of energy source used to generate heat and cooling, especially in existing infrastructure.²⁵

Despite the comprehensive nature of these legislative frameworks, none of them explicitly reference nuclear energy, and therefore do not accommodate micro-SMRs. The only potential regulatory foothold for micro-SMRs lies in the generic support for “low-emission” or “zero-emission” generation technologies, yet without specific mention, these technologies remain marginalized in policy implementation.

Decarbonizing the heating sector remains one of the most complex yet vital components of the EU’s energy transition. Heat and cooling will continue to represent a core area of energy demand,

²² Key legislative instruments governing the heating sector include: the EU Strategy for Heating and Cooling (*COM/2016/51*), which promotes energy efficiency, waste heat recovery, and renewable energy integration; the Renewable Energy Directive (RED III), which mandates a yearly increase of 1.3 percentage points in the share of renewable energy in heating and cooling, the Energy Efficiency Directive (Directive 2012/27/EU), which supports combined heat and power (CHP) and high-efficiency district heating and cooling; the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD, Directive 2010/31/EU), as amended by Directive (EU) 2023/1791, which requires new buildings to be nearly zero-energy and encourages smart heating technologies such as heat pumps.

²³ Juan Carlos Roca Reina & Johan Carlsson & Jonathan Volt & Agne Toleikyte, 2025. "Alternatives for Decarbonising High-Temperature Heating Facilities in Residential Buildings," *Energies*, MDPI, vol. 18(2), pages 1-19, January.

²⁴ European Commission: Comprehensive study of building energy renovation activities and the uptake of nearly zero-energy buildings in the EU 2019 [na: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/1.final_report.pdf].

²⁵ Wrase, Isabelle; May, Michael; Wang-Speiser, Zifei; Haase, Matthias; Meslec, Mihaela [eds.], Tagungsband zur Facility Management Konferenz Spotlight FMplus 2025 – Wissenschaft und Praxis im Dialog: Next Generation FM – How FM adds value, 2025, DOI: 10.21256/zhaw-2512.

particularly in colder climates and older building stock.²⁶ However, increasing the energy efficiency of buildings is hampered by high renovation costs, technological limitations, and the legacy of construction practices that predate current efficiency standards. Furthermore, in rural or dispersed settlements, centralized district heating becomes less viable, necessitating a shift toward localized, decentralized systems capable of converting electricity into heat and cooling on-site.

While renewable energy alone may not deliver such decentralized solutions in a cost-effective and dispatchable manner, micro-SMRs offer a promising pathway forward. Their small scale, modular design, and multi-output capabilities make them ideally suited for integration into localized heat networks, particularly those operated by municipalities or energy communities. However, in the absence of explicit policy support, local governments and communities lack the strategic guidance necessary to consider micro-SMRs as viable alternatives.

To unlock their full potential, micro-SMRs must be recognized in EU heating and cooling legislation and policy instruments as legitimate low-emission heat sources. This policy recognition could stimulate demand-side interest, enabling technology providers to propose innovative business models, including long-term lease agreements or energy-as-a-service contracts that eliminate the need for upfront capital investment.

For such models to scale, local and regional authorities require legal and policy certainty. Strategic signaling at the EU level—through inclusion in funding frameworks, regulatory roadmaps, and heating and cooling strategies—is essential. Only then can micro-SMRs transition from a technological possibility to a policy-supported solution, bridging the current gap between decentralization, electrification, and sustainable heat supply.

8. The EU Hydrogen and Synthetic Fuels Market: Policy Gaps and the Untapped Role of Micro-SMRs

The EU Hydrogen Strategy²⁷ envisions hydrogen not only as a clean fuel for transport and industry but also as a flexibility-enabling technology supporting the stability of electricity systems with high shares of renewable energy. The strategy draws a clear distinction between three hydrogen production pathways:

- Clean (green) hydrogen, produced via electrolysis using renewable electricity;
- Fossil-based hydrogen, produced from natural gas or coal without carbon capture;
- Low-carbon hydrogen, generated using fossil inputs but with reduced emissions through carbon capture or cleaner energy sources.

Under this strategy, the EU aims to install at least 40 GW of renewable-based hydrogen electrolysis capacity by 2030, with an additional 40 GW planned in neighboring regions. However, hydrogen production methods are varied, with significant differences in cost and emissions intensity, depending on the primary energy input and technology used. To navigate this complexity, a color-based

²⁶ Vaya Soler, A., Berthelemy, M., Verma, A., Bilbao y Leon, S., Kwong, G., Sozoniuk, V., White, A., Rouyer, V., Sexton Nick, K., Vasquez-Maignan, X., & Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development, Nuclear Energy Agency - OECD/NEA, 46, quai Alphonse Le Gallo, 92100 Boulogne Billancourt (France). (2021). Small Modular Reactors: Challenges and Opportunities.

²⁷ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions, A hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe of 8.7.2020, COM/2020/301 final.

classification has been adopted, where green denotes renewable-based hydrogen, grey is fossil-derived, and pink (or purple) refers to hydrogen generated using nuclear energy.²⁸

Notably, pink hydrogen is not currently recognized as a renewable energy source, which effectively excludes nuclear-powered hydrogen from EU-level support schemes. Furthermore, no distinction is made for hydrogen produced using SMRs, including micro-SMRs, despite their lower emissions and operational flexibility. This policy stance may significantly constrain the development of nuclear-based hydrogen production models, especially at a time when technological interest in micro-SMRs is increasing globally.²⁹

The Renewable Energy Directive III (RED III)³⁰ introduces binding sub-targets for renewable hydrogen produced from renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBOs³¹):

- In industry: 42% by 2030, rising to 60% by 2035 (subject to limited flexibility).
- In transport: a minimum 1% RFNBO share by 2030, with interim targets combining RFNBOs and biofuels (1% in 2025 and 5.5% in 2030³²).

The EU aims to achieve 10 million tonnes of renewable hydrogen production by 2030³³, positioning it as a pillar of industrial decarbonization and an alternative to fossil fuels in aviation, maritime transport, construction, and energy-intensive industry. RFNBOs are also promoted as substitutes for biomass-based fuels, including third-generation biofuels derived from algae or microorganisms.

However, these ambitions are difficult to achieve without expanding the role of nuclear energy, particularly given the enormous electricity demand associated with large-scale hydrogen and RFNBO production.³⁴ Strict RED III provisions impose "additionality," "temporal correlation," and "geographical correlation" requirements, mandating that only surplus renewable electricity (not needed on the grid) may be used for hydrogen production at the same time and place as generation.³⁵

²⁸ Singh, P., Agarwal, A.K., Thakur, A., & Sinha, R.K. (2024). Challenges and Opportunities in Green Hydrogen Production. Springer. Critics of color differentiation: Ajanovic A., Sayer M., Haas R., The economics and the environmental benignity of different colors of hydrogen, *International journal of hydrogen energy* 47(2022) 2 4136-24154; Dawood F, Anda M, Shafiullah GM. Hydrogen production for energy: an overview. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2020;45(7):3847e69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.12.059>.

²⁹ Ajanovic A., Sayer M., Haas R., The economics and ..., op. cit.; Talus K., Realism at the end of the rainbow? An argument towards diversifying hydrogen in EU regulation, *Journal of World Energy Law and Business*, 2024, 217–233 <https://doi.org/10.1093/jwelb/jwae007>.

³⁰ Directive EU 2023/2413 z 18.10.2023.

³¹ For the sake of clarity in the argument, at this stage I do not introduce a distinction between synthetic fuels and RFNBOs, while acknowledging that various definitions exist for the purposes of different EU regulations.

³² Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652, OJ L, 2023/2413, 31.10.2023

³³ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions, REPowerEU Plan, COM/2022/230 final.

³⁴ Talus, K. (2024). Realism at the end of the rainbow? An argument towards diversifying hydrogen in EU regulation. *Journal of World Energy Law and Business*, 217–233. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jwelb/jwae007>.

³⁵ Prussi, M., Noussan, M., Laveneziana, L., Chiaramonti D. (2025). The risk of increasing energy demand while pursuing decarbonisation: the case of the e-fuels for the EU aviation sector, *Transport Policy* 160(2025)154-158.

These restrictions severely limit the scalability of renewable hydrogen under current system constraints.³⁶

Projections suggest that EU electricity demand will reach 3,000–3,500 TWh by 2030 and 4,000–4,500 TWh by 2040, driven by: the electrification of transport and industry, the expansion of ICT and AI applications (e.g. data centers, storage), rising residential electricity use, notably for heat pumps.

Even under optimistic assumptions, renewables may supply only 50% of this demand, leaving a gap of 1,000–1,500 TWh.³⁷ It is therefore unrealistic to assume that excess renewable energy will be available in sufficient quantities to support large-scale hydrogen production. Instead, this electricity will likely be stored or used to stabilize the grid.

RED III foresees the importation of renewable hydrogen to meet expected demand, but this introduces concerns regarding energy security, carbon leakage, and supply chain emissions. In this context, it may be more strategic to recognize micro-SMRs as a viable domestic electricity source for hydrogen production, rather than rely on hydrogen imports from non-EU countries.

Current global experience demonstrates the technical feasibility of producing hydrogen from nuclear power, offering a dispatchable, low-emission solution to decarbonize hydrogen supply chains.³⁸ Electrolyzers co-located with micro-SMRs can reduce curtailment of nuclear output, enable seasonal energy storage, and facilitate the production of low-carbon hydrogen at scale. Despite this potential, EU policy lacks explicit recognition or support for such models.

The same challenges apply to RFNBOs. By 2050, demand for RFNBOs is projected to range from 935 to 2,270 TWh per year, spanning sectors such as: aviation, shipping, heavy-duty land transport, industrial heat and feedstocks.

Producing RFNBOs requires massive amounts of low-emission electricity.³⁹ Yet, it remains unclear how much of this energy will be "additional" or simply diverted from other sectors. The current RFNBO supply chain is not yet commercially viable, especially for synthetic gas production from hydrogen and CO₂. Similar issues affect recycled carbon fuels (RCFs) derived from waste materials, which also remain economically uncompetitive. As a result, importing RFNBOs may be necessary to meet regulatory quotas, further exposing the EU to external dependencies.

RED III provides a regulatory opt-out, allowing Member States to reduce RFNBO development pressure if they achieve targets via other energy forms. This clause could open the door for micro-SMR-powered

³⁶ Guidehouse Energy Germany GmbH, (2021). Technical assistance to assess the potential of renewable liquid and gaseous transport fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBOs) as well as recycled carbon fuels (RCFs), to establish a methodology to determine the share of renewable energy from RFNBOs as well as to develop a framework on additionality in the transport sector. Final report | Task 1 Assessment of the potential of RFNBOs and RCFs over the period 2020 to 2050 in the EU transport sector, ENER/C1/2019-418.

³⁷ IEA Renewable Energy Outlook, Enerdata - Global Energy & Electricity Demand Forecast <https://eneroutlook.enerdata.net/>, IEA Report on Renewable 2024 <https://www.iea.org/reports/renewables-2024>

³⁸ El-Emam R.S., Ozcan H., Zamfirescu C. Updates on promising thermochemical cycles for clean hydrogen production using nuclear energy. *J Clean Prod* 2020;262:121424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121424>; Ho A., Hill D., Hedengren J., Powell K. M., A nuclear-hydrogen hybrid energy system with large-scale storage: A study in optimal dispatch and economic performance in a real-world market, *Journal of Energy Storage* 51 (2022) 104510.

³⁹ Motola, V., Buffi, M., Scarlat, N., Hurtig, O., Georgakaki, A., Letout, S., Mountraki, A., Tattini, J. and Schmitz, A., Clean Energy Technology Observatory: Renewable Fuels of Non-biological Origin in the European Union - 2023 Status Report on Technology Development, Trends, Value Chains and Markets, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/998267; Bock, T. (2025). Sustainability Aspects of Powerfuels and Their Certification. In: Bullerdiek, N., Neuling, U., Kaltschmitt, M. (eds) Powerfuels. Green Energy and Technology. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-62411-7_33

hydrogen and RFNBOs, but only if the underlying energy source is formally recognized as acceptable. Additional policy domains—such as the ReFuelEU Aviation⁴⁰ and FuelEU Maritime initiatives—already require increasing shares of RFNBOs and synthetic aviation fuels (SAFs), reinforcing the urgency of clarifying eligible technologies.

Currently, only renewable-based technologies receive policy support, sidelining hybrid systems and nuclear-driven solutions. However, micro-SMRs operating within hybrid, potentially off-grid configurations could offer a flexible, scalable, and domestically controlled pathway for hydrogen and RFNBO production. Such systems would not only support the EU's climate goals in hard-to-abate sectors but also enhance resilience, reduce import dependency, and expand the range of eligible technologies within decarbonization frameworks.

9. Conclusions and policy implications

This article has shown that while micro-small modular reactors (micro-SMRs) offer considerable promise as a complementary low-carbon technology in the EU's energy transition, their deployment remains severely constrained by regulatory, financial, and institutional barriers. To unlock their potential, a recalibration of EU policy is required—one that acknowledges micro-SMRs not merely as scaled-down nuclear units, but as flexible, hybrid-ready components of a modern, decentralized energy system.

A key starting point is regulatory differentiation. The current framework, developed for large-scale nuclear installations, imposes disproportionate licensing and compliance burdens on micro-SMRs, failing to reflect their lower environmental and safety risks. Reforming this regime to align with the modular and scalable nature of micro-SMRs is essential to reducing entry barriers and deployment costs. Finance is another critical domain. The EU Taxonomy Regulation still treats micro-SMRs as transitional, which limits their access to green finance despite their low-carbon credentials. A reclassification that affirms their long-term role in climate mitigation would improve investment flows and signal policy stability. Simultaneously, integrating micro-SMRs into State aid instruments, such as Contracts for Difference (CfDs) or tailored Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), would strengthen their commercial viability, particularly within hybrid systems designed for electricity, heat, hydrogen, and synthetic fuel co-production. Importantly, micro-SMRs remain excluded from key regulatory frameworks shaping the electricity, heat, and hydrogen markets. Although the internal electricity market is founded on the principle of technological neutrality, renewables are functionally privileged through targeted incentives and infrastructure priorities. A consistent application of neutrality—extending to grid access, balancing, and system services—is necessary to position micro-SMRs as valid contributors to system resilience and clean energy expansion.

The heating sector presents a particularly untapped opportunity. As more than half of EU final energy demand is consumed in heating and cooling—still dominated by fossil fuels—micro-SMRs could play a central role in decarbonizing district and local heat networks, especially in regions unsuitable for large infrastructure or intermittent RES solutions. Yet current legislation overlooks their role entirely. The same pattern holds for hydrogen and synthetic fuels. RED III's focus on renewable hydrogen excludes nuclear-powered electrolysis from eligibility, despite evidence of its viability and relevance for meeting projected demand. Clarifying the role of micro-SMRs in this context, particularly under flexibility clauses that allow alternative compliance pathways, would improve policy coherence and supply security.

⁴⁰ Mayeres I., Proost S., Delhaye E., Novelli P., Conijn S., Gomez-Jimenez I., Rivas-Brousse D. (2023). Climate ambitions for European aviation: Where can sustainable aviation fuels bring us? *Energy Policy* 175 (2023) 113502.

In sum, this article underscores that the EU's climate and energy goals would be better served by a regulatory architecture that accommodates micro-SMRs as a permanent, integrated part of hybrid decarbonization strategies. Policy alignment across taxonomy, industrial support, market design, and sector-specific regulation is essential—not only to enable deployment, but to ensure that technological neutrality becomes a credible and operational principle guiding Europe's energy future.

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